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A new model of entrepreneurship education for engineering students

V.I. Sucala¹

University of Exeter
Exeter, United Kingdom

S. Carroll

University of Exeter
Exeter, United Kingdom

C.Z. Cory

University of Exeter
Exeter, United Kingdom

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ABSTRACT

The paper describes the process of designing and launching a new model of entrepreneurship education in engineering by a British university. The main driver behind this initiative has been engineering department's strategy to deliver education aligned to the global state-of-the-art practices, focused on user-centered design, technology-driven entrepreneurship, problem-based learning and a focus on rigor in the engineering fundamentals. This complemented the university's initiative to embed entrepreneurship across all its programmes.

Traditionally the entrepreneurship education originated in business or management schools. In the last decades many educational institutions have introduced entrepreneurial education in the engineering curriculum. There are three main models used by the first academic institutions in the United States for entrepreneurial education. A decade later, another study undertaken on more than two hundred universities in five countries suggested five models of entrepreneurship education for engineering students.

The paper is focused on the new and more complex model that has been developed, consisting in an entrepreneurship initiative pursued independently by engineering and the business school, supported by the university's innovation and business support team, and by external partnerships with entrepreneurship centres based in schools of engineering. Moreover all university's students are exposed additional extra-curricular entrepreneurship training.

The Engineering & Entrepreneurship undergraduate programme was launched in September 2018. The paper discusses the process of designing the engineering & entrepreneurship programme's innovative structure, content, and assessment, within the frame of the evolution of similar programmes.

¹ Corresponding Author
V.I. Sucala
i.sucala@exeter.ac.uk

1 INTRODUCTION

The paper describes the process of designing and launching a new model of entrepreneurship education in engineering by a British university. The main driver behind this initiative has been engineering department's strategy to deliver education aligned to the global state-of-the-art practices.

The report *The global state of the art in engineering education* [1] is particularly useful for the understanding of the role of technology-driven entrepreneurship in engineering education. According to the report's conclusions, practices such as user-centered design, technology-driven entrepreneurship, problem-based learning and a focus on rigor in the engineering fundamentals are common to the current leaders in engineering education. The engineering curricula of the future will become more socially-relevant and outward-facing by emphasising student choice, multidisciplinary learning and societal impact, coupled with a breadth of student experience outside the classroom, outside traditional engineering disciplines and across the world. Therefore it can be concluded that entrepreneurship and innovation in engineering are features that characterise the education delivered by the current leaders in engineering education and are also socially-relevant and outward facing. This is one of the main arguments behind the strategic decision to launch a new undergraduate programme in Engineering and Entrepreneurship. This complemented the university's initiative to embed entrepreneurialism across all its programmes.

1.1 Models of entrepreneurship education addressing engineering students

Traditionally the entrepreneurship education originated in business or management schools. However, in the last decades many educational institutions have introduced entrepreneurial education in the engineering curriculum. There are today more than 400 engineering schools offering some entrepreneurial and business courses [2]. Luryi et al argued that entrepreneurial education is of great benefit for engineering students, and there are three core requirements for the success of an entrepreneurship educational component:

- The entrepreneurial components should be compulsory to all engineering students and should involve hand-on business experience based on innovating engineering projects.
- The entrepreneurial activities should be based on multidisciplinary teamwork projects because mixing students from different backgrounds is adding versatility and functionality to the teams and is broadening their entrepreneurial experience.
- The entrepreneurial components should include competitive activities encouraging the engineering students to act on their talent and ideas [2].

The Standish-Kuon & Rice study outlined the approaches taken more than two decades ago by academic institutions in the United States and suggested a typology of three models [3]. The authors investigated how traditional science and engineering students were taught entrepreneurship at six American universities. The most important objectives of teaching technology entrepreneurship were new venture creation and, to a lesser degree, research. The most important drivers behind the initiative were internal champions and interest on the part of alumni and current students, while the lack of elective credits in the engineering curriculum was identified as the most common barrier. The three models outlined by the authors have as their distinctive characteristic the location of the entrepreneurship programmes. For the Business School model the entrepreneurship education is delivered by the business

school, the technological entrepreneurship curriculum being developed through active collaboration with engineering school, The Engineering School model has the engineering entrepreneurship education based in the engineering school, co-existing with other entrepreneurship courses offered by the business school. In the Multi-School model the technological entrepreneurship curriculum is developed through active collaboration of business school and one or more technical schools.

Another study undertaken on more than two hundred universities in five countries suggested five models of entrepreneurship education for engineering students [4]. The purpose of this research was to determine if the Standish-Kuon & Rice typology was representative of present-day entrepreneurship initiatives for engineering students, and if this typology could be applied to other entrepreneurship initiatives for engineering students outside the United States. The authors argued that a total of five models were used to develop entrepreneurship initiatives for engineering undergraduates. These results showed that the Standish-Kuon & Rice typology required updating to reflect present-day initiatives for engineering undergraduates. These findings, as a result, laid the foundation for the emergence of a new typology, which was subsequently entitled the Entrepreneurial Engineering Education, or EEE, typology. In addition to the three models identified by Standish-Kuon & Rice, Fraser et al all added two other models. The External Partnership model is similar with the Engineering School model but the development of entrepreneurship initiatives stemmed from collaborative efforts between the home institution and external partners such as external networks that supported the development of entrepreneurship education, local organizations that contributed resources to entrepreneurship initiatives, or other tertiary-level academic institutions. The Institution model described entrepreneurship initiatives derived from efforts to educate the entire student body about entrepreneurship, regardless of the degree the students are enrolled in.

The history evolution and success of embedding enterprise and entrepreneurship in the British engineering education had been also investigated for almost two decades. Substantial evidence for the effectiveness of innovative programmes has been identified but it has been also argued that it would be difficult to embed such programme in the UK for few reasons such as: resource limitations, lack of training in synergistic methods, finding suitable entrepreneurs to take part in the programme and finding space in the timetable and curriculum [5]. Delivering successful content related to enterprise appears to depend on appointment of non-traditional staff [6] which is a challenging issue in the highly competitive environment in British higher education. According to the same authors, company related knowledge should be incorporated in 'enterprise tracks' along the whole degree rather than in just few isolated modules, the lecturers should be members of the engineering departments rather than of the business schools, and students should be provided with knowledge, skills and enterprise experiences in a way that connects to the core subject.

2 DRIVERS OF CHANGE

In this particular case, the Engineering & Entrepreneurship programme had few external drivers. The first one has been an alumnus of one of the university's engineering programmes who have had a strong entrepreneurial record, and who supported the initial design and launch of the programme. This support consisted in a philanthropic donation that has been secured by the university in 2017. The donation aimed to trail-blaze a new approach to entrepreneurship which helps to catalyse a university-wide transformation in all faculties' approaches to entrepreneurship

education. Following this event, the initial structure of the Engineering & Entrepreneurship programme was designed in 2017-18 and the advertising campaign and recruitment have started at the end of 2017. The process of designing the undergraduate programme was centred on its innovative structure, content, and assessment, integrated with consistent extra-curricular activities.

The highly competitive environment and the need to keep and improve the position within the group of research intensive British universities has been the second driver of change. Therefore the engineering department has embarked into a comprehensive review process aiming to deliver an exceptional experience for students. Its starting point was the need to improve engineering education aligned to the current world's best practices and to the future trends of engineering education and as well aligned with the university's education strategy. The review and re-design process has started in 2017 and it aims to launch the new engineering programmes in 2020.

Calls for change of the traditional engineering education content and methods are not new. In October 2006 the Journal of Engineering Education published the Special Report entitled *The Research Agenda for the New Discipline of Engineering Education* [7]. According to its authors, a transformational change rather than incremental improvements in the way engineering students are recruited and educated is acutely needed in order to be able to confront future challenges. This transformational change must be grounded on 'rigorous research-based approach to our educational system, similar to the way in which research is performed and used in the traditional engineering disciplines'. While the need to ground transformational decisions on hard evidence is undisputable, collecting relevant evidence on the educational system has been a challenging issue especially in the wide and diverse area of engineering. However, the relatively significant body of knowledge summarised briefly in the Introduction has been extremely useful in this endeavour.

Besides the comprehensive review of the existing engineering programmes which is discussed by another paper, the new Engineering & Entrepreneurship programme is a critical element of this process. The overall review process has also provided the opportunity to embed entrepreneurship elements in all engineering programmes as it will be described below.

3 ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR ENGINEERS

Based on all these arguments discussed above, a new model of entrepreneurship education of engineering students has been developed, consisting in an entrepreneurship initiative pursued independently by engineering department, supported by the university's innovation and business support team, and by external partnerships with entrepreneurship centres based in schools of engineering of two US universities with a strong record in entrepreneurship education.

3.1 Entrepreneurship for all engineering students

In this education model used by this university all engineering students complete a common first year which heavily emphasises fundamental engineering science and mathematics. Entrepreneurship has historically not featured at all within the engineering curriculum. In the new structure a thread of entrepreneurship is running through years 1 and 2 with dedicated modules that develop students' skillset and awareness of topics such as rapid product and prototype development, company formation and professional networking. Two modules (courses) have been developed for this purpose: *Entrepreneurship Skills Development 1* and *2*. In these modules all

students will work in teams as businesses bidding to win a tender from a client to design and manufacture a product. These products will be aligned to existing companies that are represented on the department's industrial advisory group, and amongst the portfolio of companies engineering department currently works with. Assessment of the module will be authentic to real-world situations and will encourage students to think about materials, efficiency, sustainability, durability and profitability. They will also give a presentation to pitch their idea, develop drawings and write a report on the development process.

3.2 The main features of the Engineering & Entrepreneurship programme

Following the year 1 which is common to all engineering programmes, specific entrepreneurship content will be delivered in years 3 and 4. Utilising problem based learning, students will be presented with a selection of engineering problems that industrial partners are currently facing. In addition to academic study related to the engineering principles behind the problems, students will also have input from innovators and engineering entrepreneurs through seminars, guest lectures and workshops to help develop the values, spirit and skills essential to entrepreneurial thinking and idea development. This includes modules such as *Introduction in Economics and Company Finance*, *Technology Entrepreneurship*, *Industrial Awareness and Problem Solving*, and *Global Entrepreneurial Marketing*.

At the end of year 3 the students will have the opportunity to compete for 10 awards made annually in the year 4 of the programme. Each award worth of £12,000 will equip the winning students with the time and space they need to launch their business. This innovative structure will see selected students truly learning by doing as they start-up their own businesses based on the ideas developed over the third year. The successful students will be part of a dynamic learning environment in offices alongside high-technology businesses undertaking research and development. Each student will be assigned a mentor from industry in addition to an academic tutor from the engineering department. There will be no formal teaching on this module as it is entirely student-led. Assessment will be made through the creation and maintenance of a Professional Development Portfolio containing business plans, designs, market research and marketing plans, finance and tax documents pertaining to business administration, and several critically reflective accounts of their entrepreneurship at key stages across the year. Successful completion of the module is not tied to the success of the business, instead it is based on the engagement and critical reflection of the student, whatever the outcome. The module runs across all terms of year 4. If not successful in their bidding the student will have a normal taught year 4 concluded by a final dissertation. Students following both pathways will graduate with MEng award.

A dedicated space in which students from across the university are able to experiment with technology, devices and software to develop concepts and early minimum viable product (MVP) solutions has been provided by the university. Named *The Deck*, this space is also allowing Engineering & Entrepreneurship students to collaborate on ideas is essential to help build balanced teams and blend different experiences.

Partnerships with universities abroad will provide efficient knowledge transfer from other entrepreneurship centres based in engineering schools with a consistent record. These partnerships will be providing additional content that will help students acquire the relevant knowledge and will also provide training to the academic staff.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper is presenting the process of development and the main features of a new programme in Engineering & Entrepreneurship launched by a British university. This model consists in an entrepreneurship initiative pursued independently by the engineering department, supported by the university's innovation and business support team, and by external partnerships with entrepreneurship centres based in schools of engineering. The main drivers that have motivated the university's engineering department to create and launch this programme are also described. The authors would like to acknowledge the continued efforts of their colleagues in working towards successful delivery of the new Engineering & Entrepreneurship programme.

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